

THE MINOR CATALOGUE OF HARVARD COLLEGE OBSERVATORY NOTEBOOKS

[Revised Edition, 1975]

Prepared by Joseph Timko

"Curious how we say we have no time when, of course, we have all there is — only this happens to be insufficient for the attainment of our object. In chess, Mr. Peirce, as in the world beyond this little board, time is nothing else than the ability to do and to endure."

The preparation of the present catalogue, one which it is hoped will be of use both to astronomers and to historians of astronomy, has been made possible through the generous support of the Harvard College Observatory, and especially through the patient and extensive cooperation of Dr. Martha H. Liller.

In addition, I would like to acknowledge the assistance received from the following individuals: Karen Leach, Claudia Lewis, Linda O'Connor, and Carola Sautter.

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The following information concerning each volume is given (where available) in the present catalogue (MnCHCON) in the following order:

WIDENER CATALOGUE NUMBER

ALPHANUMERICAL CODING [Series Coding]

DATE [year(s) only]

TITLE

AUTHOR(S) [for private research notebooks]

Notes are occasionally included in the catalogue itself where some clarification seems necessary; and a general description of the two collections (the Littauer collection and the Observatory collection) are provided in an appendix to the catalogue, along with a guide to the shelving of the volumes. For more detailed information on the contents of individual notebooks, consult the much more extensive MAJOR CATALOGUE OF HARVARD COLLEGE OBSERVATORY NOTEBOOKS which is to be made available in Series installments beginning in 1975.

PART I: Volumes stored in the Littauer stacks under Widener
catalogue numbers KG 11365 and KG 11366.

KG 11365.1	A 1	1848-1849	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.2	A 2	1849	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.3	A 3	1849	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.4	A 4	1849-1850	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.5	A 5	1850	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.6	A 6	1850	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.7	A 7	1850	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.8	A 8	1850-1851	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.9	A 9	1851	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.10	A 10	1851	Transit Circle Observations

KG 11365.11	A 11	1851-1852	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.12	A 12	1852	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.13	A 13	1852	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.14	A 14	1852-1853	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.15	A 15	1853-1854	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.16	A 16	1854	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.17	A 17	1854	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.18	A 18	1854-1855	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.19	A 19	1855	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.20	A 20	1855	Transit Circle Observations

KG 11365.21	A 21	1855	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.22	A 22	1855-1856	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.23	A 23	1856	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.24	A 24	1856	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.25	A 25	1856-1857	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.26	A 26	1857	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.27	A 27	1857	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.28	A 28	1857-1858	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.29	A 29	1858	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.30	A 30	1858-1859	Transit Circle Observations

KG 11365.31	A 31	1859	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.32	A 32	1859-1860	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.33	A 33	1860	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.34	A 34	1860	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.35	A 35	1860-1861	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.36	A 36	1861	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.37	A 37	1861-1862	Transit Circle Observations
KG 11365.38	A 38	1862	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.39	A 39	1862	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.40	A 40	1862	Meridian Circle Observations

KG 11365.41	A 41	1862	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.42	A 42	1862-1863	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.43	A 43	1863	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.44	A 44	1863	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.45	A 45	1863	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.46	A 46	1863	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.47	A 47	1863-1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.48	A 48	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.49	A 49	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.50	A 50	1864	Meridian Circle Observations

KG 11365.51	A 51	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.52	A 52	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.53	A 53	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.54	A 54	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.55	A 55	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.56	A 56	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.57	A 57	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.58	A 58	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.59	A 59	1864	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.60	A 60	1864-1865	Meridian Circle Observations

KG 11365.61	A 61	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.62	A 62	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.63	A 63	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.64	A 64	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.65	A 65	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.66	A 66	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.67	A 67	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.68	A 68	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.69	A 69	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.70	A 70	1865	Meridian Circle Observations

KG 11365.71	A 71	1865	Meridian Circle Observations
KG 11365.72	B 1	1849	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.73	B 2	1849	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.74	B 3	1849-1850	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.75	B 4	1850	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.76	B 5	1850	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.77	B 6	1850-1851	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.78	B 7	1851	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.79	B 8	1851	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.80	B 9	1851	Reduction of Transits

KG 11365.81	B 10	1851-1852	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.82	B 11	1852	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.83	B 12	1852	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.84	B 13	1852-1853	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.85	B 14	1853	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.86	B 15	1853-1854	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.87	B 16	1854	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.88	B 17	1854	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.89	B 18	1854-1855	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.90	B 19	1855	Reduction of Transits

KG 11365.91	B 20	1855	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.92	B 21	1855	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.93	B 22	1855-1856	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.94	B 23	1856	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.95	B 24	1856	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.96	B 25	1856	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.97	B 26	1856-1857	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.98	B 27	1857	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.99	B 28	1857	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.100	B 29	1857-1858	Reduction of Transits

KG 11365.101	B 30	1858	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.102	B 31	1858	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.103	B 32	1858-1859	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.104	B 33	1859	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.105	B 34	1859-1860	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.106	B 35	1860	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.107	B 36	1860-1861	Reduction of Transits
KG 11365.108	C 1	1849-1853	North and South Meridian Marks, and Level Readings of Transit Circle
KG 11365.109	C 2	1853-1855	North and South Meridian Marks, and Level Readings of Transit Circle
KG 11365.110	C 3	1855-1856	North and South Meridian Marks, and Level Readings of Transit Circle

	KG 11365.111	C 4	1856-1859	North and South Meridian Marks, and Level Readings of Transit Circle
	KG 11365.112	C 5	1859-1862	North and South Meridian Marks, and Level Readings of Transit Circle
	KG 11365.113	C 8	1862-1865	Instrumental Corrections for Transit Circle
	KG 11365.114	C 9	1862-1863	Computed AR of Polar Stars
	KG 11365.115	C 10	1863-1864	Computed AR of Polar Stars
	KG 11365.116	C 11	1861-1863	Chronograph Record
	KG 11365.117	C 12	1863-1864	Chronograph Record
	KG 11365.118	C 13	1864-1865	Chronograph Record
	KG 11365.119	C 14	1865-1866	Chronograph Record
n1	KG 11365.120	C 15 (C 12)	1865-1866	Meridian Circle Observations

n1: "This book seems to belong to Series C. This label was put upon it May 25, 1868." "Note: July 30, 1877. This book contains some of the same observations found in A 74, and others for dates for which there is no record in A 74. It was perhaps used to record observations made for time only, not for star places. It should be marked C 15, as there is a small book C 12." As noted in the listing, the book is marked as both C 15 and C 12; but the former designation appears the correct one.

	KG 11365.121	D 1	1849-1850	Minutes of Chronometer Expedition	
	KG 11365.122	E 1	1859-1860	Meridian Circle Observations	
	KG 11365.123	E 2	1859	Meridian Circle Observations	
	KG 11365.124	E 3	1860	Meridian Circle Observations	
	KG 11365.125	E 4	1862-1863	Declinations	
	KG 11365.126	E 5	1863-1864	Declinations	
	KG 11365.127	E 6	1857-1858	Transit Circle Observations with New Wires, and Observations on the Planet Venus in Declination	
n2	KG 11365.128	E 7	1851-1853	Transit Circle Observations	CWT
	KG 11365.129	E 8	1851	Transit Circle Observations	
	KG 11365.130	F 1	1845-1846	Moon Culminations and Transits, and Comet Observations	

n2: C. W. Tuttle

KG 11365.131	F 2	1846	Comet Observations, and Meridian Transits
KG 11365.132	F 3	1846-1847	Meridian Transits
KG 11365.133	F 4	1847-1848	Meridian Transits
KG 11365.134	F 5	1848	Meridian Transits
KG 11365.135	F 6	1849-1850	Meridian Transits, and Preliminary Reduction of Stars Used on the Chronometric Expedition in 1849-50
KG 11365.136	F 7	1844	Meridian and Prime Vertical Observations
KG 11365.137	F 8	1851	West Transit Observations
KG 11365.138	F 9	1854-1862	Prime Vertical Observations
KG 11365.139	F 10	1857-1859	Magnetic Dip Circle and Prime Vertical Observations
KG 11365.140	F 11	1858-1861	Terrestrial Magnetism Measurements

KG 11365.141	F 12a	1864	Chronograph Record
KG 11365.142	F 12b	1864	Prime Vertical Computation of Latitude
KG 11365.143	F 13	1848	Telegraph Record (Star Signals)
KG 11365.144	G 1	1851-1853	Chronometers
KG 11365.145	G 2	1853-1855	Chronometers
KG 11365.146	G 3	1855	Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks
KG 11365.147	G 4	1856-1857	Sidereal and Mean Solar Clocks
KG 11365.148	G 5	1857-1858	Sidereal and Mean Solar Clocks
KG 11365.149	G 6	1856-1860	Sidereal and Mean Solar Clocks and Chronometers
KG 11365.150	G 7	1860-1862	Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks and Chronometers

	KG 11365.151	G 8	1862-1866	Chronometers
	KG 11365.152	G a	1854	Rail Road Time
	KG 11365.153	G b	1857-1859	Trials of Pendulums and Chronometers
n3	KG 11365.154	H a	1848-1849	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.155	H a	1860-1861	Equatorial Reductions
	KG 11365.156	H 1	1846-1847	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.157	H 2	1847	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.158	H 3	1847-1848	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.159	H 4	1847-1848	Equatorial and Prime Vertical Observations
	KG 11365.160	H 5	1848	Equatorial and Prime Vertical Observations

n3: This notebook is the continuation of KG 11365.161 (H 6), and ought to be coded H 7. KG 11365.162 ought to be coded H 8, and KG 11365.163 ought to be coded H 9. The correct numbering then resumes with KG 11365.164 (H 10). Despite the numbering of this portion of the H-series, there is no portion of the Equatorial observation records which is missing.

	KG 11365.161	H 6	1848	Equatorial and Prime Vertical Observations
	KG 11365.162	H 7	1849	Magnetic, Fox Circle and Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.163	H 8	1849	Equatorial and Telegraph Observations
n4	KG 11365.164	H 10	1849-1850	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.165	H 11	1850	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.166	H 12	1850-1851	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.167	H 13	1851	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.168	H 14	1851-1852	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.169	H 15	1852	Equatorial Observations
	KG 11365.170	H 16	1852-1853	Equatorial Observations

n4: Despite the discontinuity in numbering, there is no missing notebook in the series. See n3 (p. 21) for the corrections to the numbering of the Equatorial observation records.

KG 11365.171	H 17	1853-1854	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.172	H 18	1854-1855	Equatorial Observations ,
KG 11365.173	H 19	1855-1856	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.174	H 20	1856-1857	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.175	H 21	1857	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.176	H 22	1857	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.177	H 23	1857	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.178	H 24	1857	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.179	H 25	1857-1858	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.180	H 26	1858	Equatorial Observations

KG 11365.181	H 27	1858	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.182	H 28	1858	Equatorial Observations ,
KG 11365.183	H 29	1858-1859	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.184	H 30	1859	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.185	H 31	1859-1860	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.186	H 32	1860	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.187	H 33	1860	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.188	H 34	1860	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.189	H 35	1860	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.190	H 36	1860	Equatorial Observations

KG 11365.191	H 37	1860	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.192	H 38	1860-1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.193	H 39	1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.194	H 40	1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.195	H 41	1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.196	(H 42)	1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.197	H 43	1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.198	H 44	1861	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.199	H 45	1862	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.200	H 46	1862	Equatorial Observations

KG 11365.201	H 47	1862	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.202	H 48	1862	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.203	H 49	1862-1863	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.204	H 50	1863	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.205	H 51	1863	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.206	H 52	1863-1864	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.207	H 53	1864	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.208	H 54	1864	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.209	H 55	1864-1865	Equatorial Observations
KG 11365.210	H 56	1865-1866	Equatorial Observations

Continued in .283

KG 11365.211	K 1	1852	Zone Observations (Zones 1 - 7)
KG 11365.212	K 2	1852	Zone Observations (Zones 7, - 13)
KG 11365.213	K 3	1852	Zone Observations (Zones 14 - 19, Bessel Zones)
KG 11365.214	K 4	1852-1853	Zone Observations (Zones 20 - 26)
KG 11365.215	K 5	1853	Zone Observations (Zones 27 - 33)
KG 11365.216	K 6	1853	Zone Observations (Zones 34 - 39)
KG 11365.217	K 7	1853	Zone Observations (Zones 40 - 45)
KG 11365.218	K 8	1853	Zone Observations (Zones 46 - 54)
KG 11365.219	K 9	1853	Zone Observations (Zones 55 - 62)
KG 11365.220	K 10	1853-1854	Zone Observations (Zones 65 - 84a)

KG 11365.221	K 11	1854-1855	Zone Observations (Zones 84a - 88)
KG 11365.222	K 12	1855	Zone Observations (Zones 89 - 100)
KG 11365.223	K 13	1855	Zone Observations (Zones 101 - 116)
KG 11365.224	K 14	1859	Zone Observations (Zones 1 - 6)
KG 11365.225	K 15	1859	Zone Observations (Zones 6 - 7)
KG 11365.226	K 16	1859	Zone Observations (Zones 117 - 124)
KG 11365.227	K 17	1859	Zone Observations (Zones 125 - 135)
KG 11365.228	K 18	1859-1860	Zone Observations (Zones 134 - 146)
KG 11365.229	K 19	1860	Zone Observations (Zones 147 - 149, Catalogue Stars)
KG 11365.230	K 20	1860-1861	Zone Observations

KG 11365.231	K 21	1861	Zone Observations
KG 11365.232	K 22	1861	Zone Observations
KG 11365.233	K 23	1861	Zone Observations
KG 11365.234	K 24	1861-1862	Zone Observations
KG 11365.235	K 25	1862-1863	Zone Observations
KG 11365.236	K 26	1862-1864	Zone Observations
KG 11365.237	K 27	1864	Zone Observations
KG 11365.238	L 1	1853	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 1 - 39)
KG 11365.239	K 28	1864	Zone Observations
KG 11365.240	L 2	1853	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 40 - 60, 1 - 16)

	KG 11365.241	L 3	1853	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 15 - 39)
	KG 11365.242	L 4	1853	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 40 - 56)
	KG 11365.243	L 5	1853	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 57 - 62)
	KG 11365.244	L 6	1853	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 2 - 62)
	KG 11365.245	L 7	185_	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 63 - 92)
	KG 11365.246	L 8	185_	Reduction of Zone Observations (Zones 91 - 116)
	KG 11365.247	L 9	185_	Comparisons of Zones
n5	KG 11365.248	L 10	1859	Reduction of Zones
n6	KG 11365.249	L 11	1859	Reduction of Zones
	KG 11365.250	L 12	1862-?	Special Zones and Magnitudes

n5: The notebook bears the annotation "No Reductions", and is in fact the Chronograph record of Zones.

n6: The notebook bears the annotation "Comparison of Magnitudes", but contains only one page of comparisons; the rest of the notebook continues the Chronograph record of Zones from KG 11365.248 .

	KG 11365.251	L 13	1860 (?)	Revisions of Zones: Magnitudes
	KG 11365.252	M 2	1853	Reduction of Zones
	KG 11365.253	M 3	1848-?	Gould's <u>Universal Index</u> (Book Index)
	KG 11365.254	M 5	1854-?	Tables of Corrections (Positional)
n7	KG 11365.255	M 6	1841-1855	Tables of Contents of Various Books containing Records of Observations made with various instruments
	KG 11365.256	M 7	1842-1858	Various Memoranda
n8	KG 11365.257	M 9	1854-1858	Catalogue Stars
	KG 11365.258	M 10	1855	Tables for Apportioning Instrumental Corrections
n9	KG 11365.259	M 11	1836-1850(?)	Catalogue of Stars for Zones
	KG 11365.260	M 12	1853 (?)	Reduction of all the Stars in Weisse

n7: The compilation probably dates from 1866.

n8: The notebooks records Transit Circle observations.

n9: The notebook was probably prepared in 1853.

SHELF LOCATIONS:

KG 11365 is located in Littauer Stack 376 E, in Cases III - V.

KG 11366 is located in Littauer Stack 377 W, in Cases I - IV.

Case numbering is from left to right, and shelf numbering from top to bottom. The following table gives the decimal numbers of the volumes on each shelf:

STACK	CASE	SHELF	DECIMAL NUMBERS		
376 E	III	1	KG 11365.1	to	KG 11365.42
376 E	III	2	KG 11365.43	to	KG 11365.142
376 E	III	3	KG 11365.143	to	KG 11365.236
376 E	III	4	KG 11365.237	to	KG 11365.307
376 E	III	5	KG 11365.308	to	KG 11365.371
376 E	III	6	KG 11365.372	to	KG 11365.437
376 E	IV	1	KG 11365.438	to	KG 11365.483
376 E	IV	2	KG 11365.484	to	KG 11365.530

376 E	IV	3	KG 11365.531	to	KG 11365.573
376 E	IV	4	KG 11365.574	to	KG 11365.619
376 E	IV	5	KG 11365.620	to	KG 11365.660
376 E	IV	6	KG 11365.661	to	KG 11365.709
376 E	V	1	KG 11365.710	to	KG 11365.758
376 E	V	2	KG 11365.759	to	KG 11365.808
376 E	V	3	KG 11365.809	to	KG 11365.854
376 E	V	4	KG 11365.855	to	KG 11365.903
376 E	V	5	KG 11365.904	to	KG 11365.950
376 E	V	6	KG 11365.951	to	KG 11365.999
377 W	I	1	KG 11366.000	to	KG 11366.047
377 W	I	2	KG 11366.048	to	KG 11366.094
377 W	I	3	KG 11366.095	to	KG 11366.135 *
377 W	I	4	KG 11366.136	to	KG 11366.183
377 W	I	5	KG 11366.184	to	KG 11366.227
377 W	I	6	KG 11366.228	to	KG 11366.276

* including KG 11366.127.1

377 W	II	1	KG 11366.277	to	KG 11366.321 a
377 W	II	2	KG 11366.321 b	to	KG 11366.363 **
377 W	II	3	KG 11366.364	to	KG 11366.412
377 W	II	4	KG 11366.413	to	KG 11366.465
377 W	II	5	KG 11366.466	to	KG 11366.518
377 W	II	6	KG 11366.519	to	KG 11366.584
377 W	III	1	KG 11366.585	to	KG 11366.639
377 W	III	2	KG 11366.640	to	KG 11366.697
377 W	III	3	KG 11366.698	to	KG 11366.758
377 W	III	4	KG 11366.759	to	KG 11366.804
377 W	III	5	KG 11366.805	to	KG 11366.853
377 W	III	6	KG 11366.854	to	KG 11366.914
377 W	IV	1	KG 11366.915	to	KG 11366.992
377 W	IV	2	KG 11366.993	to	KG 11366.1068
377 W	IV	3	KG 11366.1069	to	KG 11366.1073
377 W	IV	4	KG 11366.1074	to	KG 11366.1081

** including KG 11366.322 a and KG 11366.322 b